

Antibiotics in Endodontics (Part III)

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Types of antibiotics and recommended dosages in endodontics

In all the surveys carried out, amoxicillin, alone or in combination with clavulanic acid, is the preferred prescribed antibiotic in endodontic infections with systemic effects. Amoxicillin is a moderate-spectrum, bacteriolytic, β -lactam antibiotic that represents a synthetic improvement upon the original penicillin molecule. It is a good drug for orofacial infections because it is readily absorbed (better than penicillin) and can be taken with food. It is better able to resist damage from stomach acid so less of an oral dose is wasted; it also has a much broader spectrum against the gram-negative cell wall than penicillin, and appropriate blood levels are retained for a slightly longer time. Co-amoxiclav (amoxicillin/ clavulanic acid) is one of the antibiotics recommended for the treatment of odontogenic infections due to its sufficiently wide spectrum, greater antibacterial effectiveness than penicillin, low incidence of resistance, pharmacokinetic profile, tolerance and dosage and low resistance of bacteria cultivated from root canal samples. However, evidence-based guidelines recommend that due to its greater potential for the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains and association with increased risk of Clostridium difficile infection, it should be reserved for immuno compromised patients or those infections that have not responded to first-line antimicrobial therapy when provided in conjunction with operative treatment. Due to its longer half-life and more sustained serum levels, amoxicillin is taken three times a day. The recommended oral dosage of amoxicillin with or without clavulanic acid is 1000 mg loading dose followed by 500 mg every 8 hours. Quoting American Association of

Endodontists, It has been argued that amoxicillin has a broader spectrum than is required for endodontic needs and, therefore, its use in a healthy individual could contribute to the global problem of antibiotic resistance. However, this argument is old and not justified. There is no doubt that the use of antibiotics in general should be restricted to those cases where there is a clear indication for them; however, whether the selection of one type over another with a slightly wider spectrum can contribute to the global resistance problem is not well reasoned. Even more important than slightly better antimicrobial spectrum, amoxicillin is better absorbed, and can therefore be use in a lower dose and may thus reduce the gastrointestinal side effects. On the other hand, penicillin-induced diarrhoea may even further reduce antibiotic absorption, decreasing antibiotic levels in circulation and in the infected area.

In contrast Penicillin V is a narrow-spectrum antibiotic for infections caused by aerobic gram-negative cocci, facultative and anaerobic microorganisms . It has selective toxicity and exerts its antibacterial effect by the inhibition of cell wall production in bacteria. However, penicillin is not well absorbed from the intestinal tract, meaning that at least 70% of an oral dose is wasted, with diarrhoea as a frequent side effect. Penicillin is also a short-acting medication, with half of the amount circulating being removed from the body every half hour.

Baumgartner & Xia in 2003 Tested the antibiotic susceptibility on a panel of bacteria isolated from endodontic infections, the percentages of susceptibility for the 98 species analysed were 85% for penicillin V, 91% for amoxicillin, 100% for amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, 96% for clindamycin and 45% for metronidazole.

When prescribing penicillin a loading dose of 1000 mg should be administered orally followed by 500 mg every 4–6 h to achieve a steady serum level. During the endodontic treatment, following the debridement of the root canal system and drainage, significant improvement should be seen within 48–72 hours. However, if penicillin therapy is ineffective, another antibiotic should be selected, ideally following culture and sensitivity testing. Clindamycin is a good alternative. Although penicillin is generally the antibiotic of choice in infections of endodontic origin, one disadvantage associated with its use is the possibility of allergic reactions. Approximately 8% of the population have a history of penicillin allergy. In patients with a confirmed penicillin allergy history, the clinician can switch to other antimicrobial agents such as clindamycin, metronidazole and clarithromycin or azithromycin. However, dentists must not overuse non-beta-lactam antibiotics in patients with a history of penicillin allergy, without an appropriate evaluation. As a minimum, the clinician should ask about the symptoms of allergy from the patient. It must be remembered that some patients may report intolerance symptoms, that is diarrhoea or upset stomach, as an allergy.

Clindamycin belongs to the lincosamide class of antibiotics. It kills microorganisms by blocking their ribosomes. It is effective against most gram-positive aerobes and both gram-positive and gram-negative facultative bacteria and anaerobes. The distribution of this antibiotic in most body tissues is effective and has a bone concentration approximating to that in the plasma. The adult oral dosage is 600 mg loading dose followed by 300 mg every 6 hours.

Metronidazole is a nitroimidazole that is used either as an antiprotozoal agent or an antibiotic against anaerobic bacteria, and has been suggested as a supplemental medication for amoxicillin because of its excellent activity against anaerobes (American Association of Endodontists (AAE)). Because there are many bacteria resistant to metronidazole and it is not effective against aerobic and facultative bacteria, it is generally used in combination with penicillin or clindamycin. Metronidazole used in combination with penicillin or amoxicillin has been found to increase the susceptibility to 93% and 99% of bacteria, respectively. The adult oral dosage is 1000 mg loading dose followed by 500 mg every 6 hours.

Duration of antibiotic therapy

The duration of antibiotic use in endodontic infections has not been defined precisely. Even though some dental practitioners consider that bacterial infections require 'a complete course' of antibiotic therapy, there is a general tendency to administer an antibiotic for 3–7 days.

As prolonged antibiotic usage destroys the commensal flora in the oral cavity and other body sites and terminates colonization resistance, the use and duration of systemic antibiotic therapy must be reasonable. There is a common misconception that prolonged antibiotic administration is necessary even after clinical remission of the infection in order to avoid rebound infection. Endodontic infections do not rebound when the source of periapical infection is properly eradicated, which is complete debridement, irrigation and disinfection of an infected root canal. Because these types of infections persist for several days, patients receiving antibiotics should be observed on a daily basis. The only guide for determining the effectiveness of antibiotic therapy and local endodontic intervention is the clinical improvement in the patient's symptoms. When there is ample clinical evidence that the symptoms are resolving or resolved, the antibiotic therapy should be discontinued.

Despite the fact that antibiotics are very useful tools in cases posing risk for the patient, one should always bear in mind that they are not substitutes for endodontic treatment. The key to obtaining a successful result in an endodontic infection is the chemo-mechanical removal of the infecting agent from the root canal system as well as drainage of pus. The indications for antibiotic administration should be considered very carefully and only as an adjunct to endodontic treatment, which is the major and indispensable procedure for obtaining the optimum outcome in lesions of endodontic origin. When antibiotic usage is prescribed rationally and restricted to indicated cases only, favourable results are likely to be obtained for the complete eradication of the infection.

Antibiotic prophylaxis for medically compromised patients

The aim of antibiotic prophylaxis is to prevent local postoperative infections and prevent metastatic spread of infection in susceptible individuals. Most individuals do not need antibiotic prophylaxis in connection with dental care. The microorganisms are scavenged from the bloodstream within minutes up to 1 hour without causing any complications in healthy individuals. Antibiotic prophylaxis may be considered for certain patient groups with impaired immunologic function. Surgical endodontic treatment on teeth with persistent infection after orthograde treatment is considered a higher medical burden than conventional endodontic treatment and patients at risk may benefit from antibiotic prophylaxis to a greater extent.

Immuno-compromised patients

Individuals who are immuno compromised are less capable of battling infections because of an immune response that is not properly functioning. Causes of immuno deficiency can be acquired (such as leukaemia or HIV/AIDS), chronic disease (such as end-stage renal disease and dialysis or uncontrolled diabetes), medication (such as chemotherapy, radiation, steroids or immuno suppressive post-transplant medications) or genetic (such as inherited genetic defects). For most of these medical conditions, the treatment must be planned in close collaboration with physicians.

According to the guidelines of the American Heart Association, individuals who are at risk of developing infective endocarditis following an invasive dental procedure still benefit from antibiotic prophylaxis, even if little evidence exists to support its effectiveness.

Conclusions

The use of systemic antibiotics in endodontics should be limited to specific cases so as to avoid their over-prescription. They can be used as an adjunct in the treatment of apical periodontitis to prevent the spread of the infection only in acute apical abscesses with systemic involvement, and in progressive and persistent infections. Medically compromised patients are more susceptible to complication arising from endodontic infections. Thus, antibiotics should be considered in patients having systemic diseases with compromised immunity and in patients with a localized congenital or acquired altered defence capacity, such as patients with infective endocarditis, prosthetic cardiac valves, or with recent prosthetic joint replacement. Although penicillin VK, possibly combined with metronidazole to cover anaerobic strains, is still effective in most cases, amoxicillin (alone or together with clavulanic acid) is recommended because of better absorption and lower risk of side effects. In case of confirmed penicillin allergy, lincosamides, such as clindamycin, are the drug of choice.

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